

Supplementary files

Supplement A. Database search strategy

PubMed | 01/01/2013 - 03/30/2023

Search Date: March 30, 2023

Performed By: Lori Kramer

1.	"Systematic Reviews as Topic"[MeSH]	10,205
2.	"systematic review"[tiab]	260,668
3.	"scoping review"[tiab]	19,020
4.	"Strength of evidence"[tiab]	3,317
5.	"Study evaluation"[tiab]	1,040
6.	"Weight of evidence"[tiab]	2,198
7.	"Meta-Analysis"[tiab]	229,943
8.	"Evidence Synthesis"[tiab]	6,855
9.	"Research Synthesis"[tiab]	707
10.	"Systematic Map"[tiab]	103
11.	1-16 (Systematic Review)	400,501
12.	"Environmental Health"[MeSH]	27,001
13.	"Environmental Health"[tiab]	12,400
14.	"Hazardous Substances/toxicity"[MeSH]	2,304
15.	"Environmental Pollution"[MeSH]	623,215
16.	"Environmental Medicine"[MeSH]	489
17.	"Environmental Microbiology"[MeSH]	127,332
18.	17-21 (Environmental Health)	629,987
19.	framework[tiab]	355,542
20.	manual[tiab]	119,922
21.	report[tiab]	2,083,663
22.	recommend*[tiab]	831,822
23.	guideline[tiab]	79,594
24.	protocol[tiab]	408,900
25.	"Environment and Public Health/methods"[MeSH]	406,920
26.	"Models, Theoretical"[MeSH]	1,941,686
27.	"Risk Assessment/methods"[MeSH]	39,627
28.	22-32 (Framework/Methodology)	5,705,356
29.	11 AND 18 (SR & EH)	6,186
30.	11 AND 28 (SR & Framework)	116,599
31.	18 AND 28 (EH & Framework)	196,804
32.	11 AND 18 AND 28 (SR & EH & Framework)	2,010
33.	English[Filter]	1,979
34.	Timeframe: 01/01/2013 - 03/30/2023	1,508

EMBASE | 01/01/2013 - 03/30/2023

Search Date: March 30, 2023

Performed By: Lori Kramer

-	English[Filter]
1.	"Systematic Reviews as Topic"[MeSH]
2.	"systematic review"[tiab]
3.	"scoping review"[tiab]
4.	systematic[tiab]
5.	overview[tiab]
6.	review[tiab]
7.	synthes*[tiab]
8.	"Strength of evidence"[tiab]
9.	"Study evaluation"[tiab]
10.	"Weight of evidence"[tiab]
11.	"Meta-Analysis"[tiab]
12.	"Evidence Synthesis"[tiab]
13.	"Research Synthesis"[tiab]
14.	"Systematic Map"[tiab]
15.	1-14 (Systematic Review)
16.	"Environmental Health"[MeSH]
17.	"Environmental Health"[tiab]
18.	"Hazardous Substances/toxicity"[MeSH]
19.	"Environmental Pollution"[MeSH]
20.	16-19 (Environmental Health)
21.	framework[tiab]
22.	manual[tiab]
23.	report[tiab]
24.	recommend*[tiab]
25.	"guideline"[Publication Type]
26.	protocol[tiab]
27.	method*[tiab]
28.	"Models, Theoretical"[MeSH]
29.	"Risk Assessment/methods"[MeSH]
30.	20-29 (Framework/Methodology)
31.	15 AND 20 (SR & EH)
32.	15 AND 30 (SR & Framework)
33.	20 AND 30 (EH & Framework)
34.	15 AND 20 AND 30 (SR & EH & Framework)

Cochrane | Last 10 Years (Jan 2013 - Jan 2023)

Search Date: 3/29/2023

Performed By: Lori Krammer

- English[Filter]	
1.	[mh "Systematic Reviews as Topic"] 97
2.	"systematic review":ti,ab 5,570
3.	"scoping review":ti,ab 122
4.	systematic:ti,ab 17,121
5.	overview:ti,ab 2,739
6.	review:ti,ab 63,924
7.	synthes*:ti,ab 7,103
8.	"Strength of evidence":ti,ab 118
9.	"Study evaluation":ti,ab 20,352
10.	"Weight of evidence":ti,ab 27
11.	"Meta-Analysis":ti,ab 11,396
12.	"Evidence Synthesis":ti,ab 162
13.	"Research Synthesis":ti,ab 13
14.	"Systematic Map":ti,ab 15
15.	1-14 (Systematic Review) 132,741
16.	[mh "Environmental Health"] 191
17.	"Environmental Health":ti,ab 130
18.	[mh "Environmental Pollution"] 2,508
19.	16-19 (Environmental Health) 5,015
20.	framework:ti,ab 8,190
21.	manual:ti,ab 20,035
22.	report:ti,ab 204,711
23.	recommend*:ti,ab 68,398
24.	protocol:ti,ab 106,096
25.	method*:ti,ab 628,060
26.	[mh "Models, Theoretical"] 14,246
27.	20-26 (Framework/Methodology) 950,262
28.	15 AND 19 (SR & EH) 207
29.	15 AND 27 (SR & Framework) 75,983
30.	19 AND 27 (EH & Framework) 1,896
31.	15 AND 19 AND 27 (SR & EH & Framework) 35

Supplement B. Gray literature search strategy

Date searched	Organization name & URL	Search strategy(s) / terms searched	# of items retrieved*	# of items included
3/13/23	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality https://www.ahrq.gov	Searched: “systematic review methods”; “environmental health”	208; 135	1
3/13/23	Air & Waste Management Association (AWMA) https://www.awma.org	Reviewed contents of “Publications” navigation tab Summary of A&WMA Critical Reviews	51	0
3/13/23	American Water Works Association https://www.awwa.org	Searched: “systematic review”; Reviewed contents of “policy statements” area of website	3; 40	0
3/13/23	British Columbia Ministry of Health https://www2.gov.bc.ca/gov/content/home	Searched: “systematic review”; “evidence review” environment; “evidence review” “method”; “evidence review” “manual”; Reviewed contents of “B.C. Guidelines” area of website	1; 123; 138; 78; 1	1
3/13/23	Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health (CADTH) https://www.cadth.ca/about-cadth	Searched: “systematic review” “environment” “method”	349	0
3/13/23	Canadian Standards Association (CSA) https://www.csagroup.org/about-csa-group/	Reviewed contents of “standards research” area of website	116	0
3/15/23	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) - National Center for Environmental Health (NCEH) https://www.cdc.gov/nceh/	Searched: “systematic review” “environmental health”		

Date searched	Organization name & URL	Search strategy(s) / terms searched	# of items retrieved*	# of items included
3/15/23	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) - Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR) https://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/features/	Reviewed contents of “policies” area of website	5	
3/13/23	Chartered Institute of Environmental Health (CIEH) https://www.cieh.org	Searched: “systematic review”; “evidence review”	100; 100	0
3/15/23	Children’s Environmental Health Network (CEHN) https://cehn.org	Searched: “systematic review”; Reviewed contents of “Research” area of website	4; 15	0
3/15/23	Collaboration for Environmental Evidence https://environmentalevidence.org	Searched: “systematic review”; Reviewed contents of “Resources for Authors” area of website	70; 7	1
3/15/23	Environmental and Occupational Health Sciences Institute (EOHSI) https://eohsi.rutgers.edu	Searched: “systematic review”; Reviewed contents of “Divisions” area of website	7; 5	0
5/3/23	Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) https://www.epa.gov/	Searched “systematic review environmental health”; “systematic review guidelines”, “systematic review handbook”	1442; 4576; 1192	0
5/2/23	Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) - Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS)	Taken from Source Framework folder	N/A	1
5/2/23	Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) - Report on Carcinogens (RoC)	Taken from NTP website	N/A	1
3/15/23	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC)	Searched: “systematic review” “manual” with filter “EDCD corporate”	106	0

Date searched	Organization name & URL	Search strategy(s) / terms searched	# of items retrieved*	# of items included
	https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en			
5/2/23	European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en	Reviewed publications section of the website with methodology filter; Searched “systematic review guideline”	127; 1578	3
5/1/23	Federal Register https://www.federalregister.gov	Searched: “systematic review”; “systematic review guidelines”; “systematic review environmental health”; systematic review handbook”	2189; 1019; 890; 208	0
5/1/23	GovInfo https://www.govinfo.gov	Searched “systematic review environmental health”;	4844; 4728	0
5/1/23	Health Canada https://www.canada.ca/en/health-canada.html	Searched “systematic review environmental health”; “systematic review guidelines”	5253; 798	0
3/15/23	Health Effects Institute (HEI) https://www.healtheffects.org	Searched: “systematic review”	419	0
4/28/23	Health Quality Ontario https://www.hqontario.ca	Searched: “systematic review”; “guidelines”; “handbook”	2566; 1134; 154	0
4/28/23	International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) https://www.iarc.who.int	Reviewed “publications’ section of website and Searched “systematic review”; “systematic review methods”; “guidelines”; “handbook”	516; 67; 12; 82; 96	0
4/28/23	International Federation of Environmental Health (IFEH) https://www.ifeh.org/index.html	Reviewed “Publications” section of website and Searched “systematic review”; “systematic review methods”; “guidelines”; “handbook”	95; 25; 23; 100; 16	0

Date searched	Organization name & URL	Search strategy(s) / terms searched	# of items retrieved*	# of items included
4/27/23	National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, Medicine (NAEM) https://www.nationalacademies.org	Reviewed “Environment and Environmental Health” section of website and Searched “systematic review”	1292; 1469	3
4/27/23	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) https://www.nice.org.uk/about	Reviewed “guidance” section of the website; Searched “NICE guidelines” with published handbook	1736; 1150	1
4/27/23	National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) https://www.cdc.gov/NIOSH/	Searched “systematic review”; “systematic methods review”; “environmental health”; “guidelines”; “handbook”	8; 3; 392; 205; 17	
4/27/23	National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS) - National Toxicology Program (NTP) https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov	Reviewed “testing regulations and guidelines” section of website, Searched “systematic review” with general NTP and literature analysis filter; “handbook”	166; 583; 104	1
4/27/23	Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) https://www.osha.gov	Searched “systematic review”; “guidelines”; “environmental health”	0; 11; 0	0
4/27/23	Public Health Agency of Canada (PHAC) https://www.canada.ca/en/public-health.html	Searched “systematic review environmental health”	5,303	0
4/26/23	Science.gov https://www.science.gov	Searched “systematic review”; “environmental health”; “systematic review environmental health”; “systematic review guidelines”	937; 955; 531; 630	1
4/26/23	Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network (SIGN) https://www.sign.ac.uk	Reviewed “Our guidelines” section of website; “Methodology” section of website; “Publications” section of website, Searched “systematic review”	50; 1; 55; 67	1

Date searched	Organization name & URL	Search strategy(s) / terms searched	# of items retrieved*	# of items included
4/26/23	US Climate and Health Alliance https://usclimateandhealthalliance.org	Searched “systematic review”; systematic review methods; “evidence review”	24; 9; 43	0
4/26/23	US Preventive Services Taskforce https://www.uspreventiveservicestaskforce.org/uspstf/	Searched “systematic review”; environmental health”	133; 17	0
4/26/23	World Health Organization (WHO) https://www.who.int	Searched “systematic review methods”; “systematic review”;	0; 189;	0

Supplement C. Eligibility criteria for title/abstract and full text screening

Include: Documents reporting on frameworks, methods, approaches, process manuals, or guidance for the conduct systematic reviews in environmental health

Exclude:

- Published or made public before 2013
- Documents that do not describe a framework/approach to systematic reviews
 - Documents referencing a framework/approach to systematic reviews without any description of the framework are excluded
- Documents addressing scoping reviews or scoping review methods
- Documents addressing evidence reviews in veterinary medicine
- Approaches or methods that are not intended for application in environmental health
- Tools for assessing risk of bias
- Duplicate reports on the same framework
 - Documents reporting on older versions of the same framework are excluded

Supplement D. Frameworks excluded during full text screening

Author	Year	Framework Title	Source	Exclusion Rationale
AHRQ	2014	Methods Guide for Effectiveness and Comparative Effectiveness Reviews	Gray Literature	Not applicable to environmental health
AHRQ	2014	Methods Guide for Effectiveness and Comparative Effectiveness Reviews	References	Duplicate
AHRQ	2018	Methods Guide for Comparative Effectiveness Reviews: Quantitative Synthesis -- An Update	References	Method for meta-analysis in isolation
Arksey	2005	Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework	References	Outside of date range (2013-2023); addresses scoping reviews
Bae	2014	An overview of systematic reviews of diagnostic tests accuracy	References	Systematic review framework for diagnostic test accuracy; not applicable to environmental health
Baldacci	2018	Environmental and individual exposure and the risk of congenital anomalies: a review of recent epidemiological evidence	Database Search	Not a systematic review framework
BCMh	2017	Guidelines and Protocols Advisory Committee Handbook	Grey Literature	Not applicable to environmental health
Beronius	2015	Using systematic reviews for hazard and risk assessment of endocrine disrupting chemicals	Database Search	Commentary with no systematic review framework
Boland	2018	Development and validation of the PEPPER framework (Prenatal Exposure PubMed ParsER) with applications to food additives	Database Search	No systematic review framework; discusses literature search step of a systematic review in isolation
Brozek	2021	GRADE Guidelines 30: the GRADE approach to assessing the certainty of modeled evidence--An overview in the context of health decision-making	References	No systematic review framework; GRADE approach to determine certainty of evidence
Canu	2020	State of knowledge on the occupational exposure to carbon nanotubes	Database Search	No systematic review framework; this systematic review uses the IARC approach (already extracted)
CEE	2013	Guidelines for systematic reviews in environmental management (Version 4.2)	References	Outdated version

Author	Year	Framework Title	Source	Exclusion Rationale
CEE	2018	Guidelines and standards for evidence synthesis in environmental management (Version 5.0)	References	Outdated version
Cochrane	2008	Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions	References	Outside of date range (2013-2023)
COHERE	2016	Checklist for One Health Epidemiological Reporting of Evidence (COHERE)	References	Does not describe systematic review methods
Danopoulos	2020	Microplastic contamination of drinking water: A systematic review	Database Search	Not a systematic review framework; is a systematic review itself, uses PRISMA-P (already extracted)
DeLuca	2021	Human exposure pathways to poly- and perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) from indoor media: A systematic review protocol	Database Search	Protocol for an systematic review with no framework presented
DeLuca	2022	Human exposure pathways to poly- and perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) from indoor media: A systematic review	Database Search	Systematic review with no framework presented
Denzin	2018	The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research (version 5)	References	Not applicable to environmental health
EFSA	2015	Principles and process for dealing with data and evidence in scientific assessments	References	Does not describe systematic review methods
EFSA	2020	Draft framework for protocol development for EFSA's scientific assessments	Gray Literature	Methods for protocol development; redundant with EFSA framework for systematic reviews (already extracted)
EFSA	2022	Review of state-of-the-art AI tools and methods for screening, extracting and evaluating NAMs literature in the context of chemical risk assessment	Gray Literature	No systematic review framework; only looks at incorporation of AI tools into discrete steps of a systematic review
EPA	2018	Application of systematic review in TSCA risk evaluations	References	Outdated version
EPA	2022	IRIS Handbook	Gray Literature	Duplicate
EPPI-Centre	2009	A systematic map of the research on the relationship between Obesity and Sedentary Behaviour in young people	References	Systematic review with no framework presented; outside of date range (2013-2023)
Hoffmann	2006	Toward an evidence-based toxicology	References	Commentary with no systematic

Author	Year	Framework Title	Source	Exclusion Rationale
				review framework; outside of date range (2013-2023)
Hooijmans	2014	Meta-Analysis of Animal Studies: An Introduction of a Valuable Instrument to Further Improve Healthcare	References	Method for meta-analysis in isolation
IOM	2011	Finding What Works in Health Care: Standards for Systematic Reviews	References	Duplicate (NASEM 2011); outside of date range (2013-2023)
JWEG	2015	The Production of Quick Scoping Reviews and Rapid Evidence Assessments	References	Does not describe systematic review methods
Klimisch	1996	A Systematic Approach for Evaluating the Quality of Experimental Toxicological and Ecotoxicological Data	References	No systematic review framework; outside of date range (2013-2023)
Lincoln	Undated	Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions, and emerging confluences	References	No systematic review framework
Lincoln	2017	Evidence for Policy and Practice Information and Coordinating Centre (EPPI-Centre)	References	Full text unavailable
LRA	2020	LRA Toolkit Instructions	References	Data appraisal toolkit; does not describe systematic methods
Mengist	2020	Method for conducting systematic literature review and meta-analysis for environmental science research (PALSAR)	Database Search	Topic is human impact on the environment w/no discussion of human health outcomes
Mengist	2020	Method for conducting systematic literature review and meta-analysis for environmental science research	References	Duplicate
Merkow	2021	Reporting Guidelines: The Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) Framework	References	No systematic review framework
Moher	2015	Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015 statement	References	Not systematic review methods; framework for review protocols
Nanninga	2019	Impact of Public Smoking Bans on Social Inequalities in Children's Exposure to Tobacco Smoke at Home: An Equity-Focused Systematic Review	Database Search	Not a systematic review framework; is a systematic review itself, uses PRISMA-E (already extracted)
NASEM	2011	Finding What Works in Health Care:	Gray Literature	Outside of date range (2013-2023)

Author	Year	Framework Title	Source	Exclusion Rationale
		Standards for Systematic Reviews		
NASEM	2021	The Use of Systematic Review in EPA's Toxic Substances Control Act Risk Evaluations	Gray Literature	Background/discussion; clarifies rationale for our study and provides aspirational recommendations
NASEM	2022	Advancing the Framework for Assessing Causality of Health and Welfare Effects to Inform National Ambient Air Quality Standard Reviews	Gray Literature	Not a systematic review framework
NHS	2008	SIGN 50: A guideline developer's handbook	Gray Literature	Scope is explicitly limited to health care interventions; outside of date range (2013-2023)
NICE	2012	Methods for the development of NICE public health guidance (third edition)	References	Outdated Version
NTP	Undated	NTP Process for Preparation of the Report on Carcinogens, 15th Edition	Gray Literature	Outdated Version
NTP	2015	Handbook for Preparing Report on Carcinogens Monographs	References	Outdated version
Peters	2020	Updated methodological guidance for the conduct of scoping reviews (JBI)	References	Not systematic review methods - scoping reviews
Prueitt	2022	Systematic review of the association between long-term exposure to fine particulate matter and mortality	Database Search	No systematic review framework
Rooney	2014	Systematic Review and Evidence Integration for Literature-Based Environmental Health Science Assessments	Database Search	Derivative of NTP OHAT framework
Rooney	2014	Systematic Review and Evidence Integration for Literature-Based Environmental Health Science Assessments	References	Duplicate
Shea	2008	AMSTAR is a reliable and valid measurement tool to assess the methodological quality of systematic reviews	References	Outside of our date range (2013-2023)
Sheehan	2016	Ambient air pollution epidemiology systematic review and meta-analysis: A review of reporting and methods practice	Database Search	Duplicate

Author	Year	Framework Title	Source	Exclusion Rationale
Soskolne	2021	Toolkit for detecting misused epidemiological methods	References	No systematic review framework
Stroup	2000	Meta-analysis of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (MOOSE)	References	No systematic review framework; outside of our date range (2013-2023)
Sutton	2020	Reviews in environmental health: how systematic are they?	Database Search	Commentary with no systematic review framework
Thayer	2022	Use of systematic evidence maps within US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS) program: advancements to date and looking ahead	Database Search	Duplicate (published description of IRIS)
Tricco	2018	PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation	References	Not systematic review methods - scoping reviews
Truman	2000	Developing the Guide to Community Preventive Services--Overview and Rationale	References	Outside of date range (2013-2023)
Tsuda	2022	Demonstrating the undermining of science and health policy after the Fukushima nuclear accident by applying the Toolkit for detecting misused epidemiological methods	References	No systematic review framework
Vandenberg	2018	A proposed framework for the systematic review and integrated assessment (SYRINA) of endocrine disrupting chemicals	Database Search	Duplicate
Venkataramanan	2018	Venkataramanan 2018	Database Search	No systematic review framework; limited to quality appraisal
Weinstein	2003	Principles of Good Practice for Decision Analytic Modeling in Health-Care Evaluation: Report of the ISPOR Task Force on Good Research Practices--Modeling Studies	References	No systematic review framework; outside of date range (2013-2023)
Whaley	2020	Recommendations for the conduct of systematic reviews in toxicology and environmental health research (COSTER)	References	Duplicate
Whaley	2022	CREST_Triage Systematic Review Triage Report (for protocols and final SRs)	References	Tool for editorial triage, no systematic review framework

Systematic Review Methods in Environmental Health: a critical interpretive synthesis to inform the evolution of systematic review guidance

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Author	Year	Framework Title	Source	Exclusion Rationale
WHO	2017	WHO Guidelines on Protecting Workers from Potential Risks of Manufactured Nanomaterials	References	Duplicate (followed WHO 2012)
Woodruff	2014	The Navigation Guide Systematic Review Methodology: A Rigorous and Transparent Method for Translating Environmental Health Science into Better Health Outcomes	References	Duplicate
Zhang	2023	Influencing factors of antibiotic resistance genes removal in constructed wetlands: A meta-analysis assisted by multivariate statistical methods	Database Search	No systematic review framework

Supplement E. Data extraction form and example of data extraction (in italics)

General Information												
Author / Year	Framework Name	Extractor	Reviewer	Topic area	Year published / public	Iteration	Organization	Funding source	Geographic location	Rationale or purpose	Has the framework been validated?	Framework influences
Last name, pub yr	Name of framework as reported	Person extracting	Person reviewing	Area of EH framework developed to address	Year published or made public	Framework version #	Primary sponsor	Funding source for study or report	Country where framework developed	Problem statement, justification of framework	Y/N, comment if validation is mentioned but not completed	Predecessor frameworks from which the source framework was derived; other influences noted by the authors, if available
<i>Woodruff 2014</i>	<i>The Navigation Guide Systematic Review Methodology</i>	<i>LK</i>	<i>ES</i>	<i>Environmental health (general)</i>	<i>2014</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>UCSD</i>	<i>See Table 2</i>	<i>USA</i>	<i>"Expediting the development of evidence-based recommendations for preventing harmful environmental exposures"</i>	<i>Y: case study described</i>	<i>"Developed by coupling the rigor of systematic review methods being used by the clinical sciences to the "bottom line" approach to research synthesis being used by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC 2006)."</i>

Framework Components/Domains

Research question

Protocol development

Does the framework address defining a research question? (Y/N)	Who's responsible for developing the research question (describe)	Any guidance for integrating evidence from non-human exposures? (Y/N)	Does the framework address a Protocol? (Y/N)	Who is responsible for developing the protocol? (describe)	What methods are used to formulate the protocol? (list)	Does the framework specify a review process for the protocol? (Y/N)	Does it specify whether a protocol should be published / public? (Y/N)	What methods are used to publish or make public the protocol? (list)
Y	<i>interdisciplinary team (first application used a team of nine scientists from academia and the U.S. EPA)</i>	<i>Y: quality of evidence evaluated separately for human / nonhuman exposures, then diverse evidence streams combined</i>	Y	<i>interdisciplinary team (systematic review team)</i>	<i>PECO (Participants, exposure, comparator, and outcomes)</i>	N	N	N/A

Search strategy

Does the framework address a literature search strategy? (Y/N)	Who is responsible for developing the search strategy? (describe)	How many databases are searched? (list)	Does the framework require or recommend a grey literature search? (Y/N)	Does it require / recommend any specific search restrictions? (Y/N)	Does it require / recommend justification for search restrictions? (Y/N)
<i>Y: not structured, but they detail some aspects of their process (using filters, contacting authors, etc.)</i>	<i>Systematic review team</i>	<i>NR</i>	<i>Y: mentions "nonsystematic literature review"</i>	<i>Y: search filter for animal studies in use in the preclinical literature</i>	<i>Y: search filter for animal studies "greatly expedited the development of a search for relevant animal studies"</i>

Screening

Does the framework address study selection/screening? (Y/N)	Does it require / recommend development of specific eligibility criteria? (Y/N)	Does it require / recommend any specific restrictions on the types of eligible study designs? (Y/N)	Does it require / recommend justification for study design eligibility restrictions? (Y/N)	Does the framework require or recommend study selection in duplicate? (Y/N)	Who is responsible for performing title and abstract screening? (describe)	Is AI incorporated into the TIAB screening process? (Y/N)	Who is responsible for performing full text screening? (describe)	Is AI incorporated into the full text screening process? (Y/N)	Does it require / recommend a specific software platform for study selection? (Y/N)	Does it describe a process for reaching consensus between raters/resolving inter-rater conflicts? (Y/N)	Does it require / recommend documentation of studies that were excluded with justification? (Y/N)
<i>Y: based on "a PECO statement from which we developed very</i>	Y	N	N	N	<i>Research team; software</i>	<i>Y: AI not mentioned specifically, but a</i>	<i>Research team</i>	<i>NR</i>	N	N	<i>Y: Documentation required for all</i>

<i>explicit criteria used to efficiently screen titles and abstracts"</i>					<i>program used to assist</i>	<i>software program was used</i>					<i>judgements</i>
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Data extraction

Does the framework address data extraction? (Y/N)	Does it require or recommend data extraction in duplicate? (Y/N)	Who is responsible for performing data extraction? (describe)	Is AI incorporated into the extraction process? (Y/N)	Does it require or recommend a specific software platform for data extraction? (Y/N)	Does it describe a process for reaching consensus between extractors / resolving inter-extractor conflicts? (Y/N)
<i>Y: Mentioned but not detailed - "by applying a method that seeks to extract the exact same information, laid out in the same transparent way"</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>NR</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>N: Documentation previously mentioned applies here as well</i>

Data synthesis

Does the framework address methods for data synthesis? (Y/N)	Does the framework provide guidance for selection of appropriate methods for statistical combination of results? (Y/N)	Is a specific approach recommended or required? (describe)
<i>N</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>N/A</i>

Risk of bias assessment

Does the framework address risk of bias assessment? (Y/N)	Does it require / recommend a specific tool, process, or method for assessing risk of bias in randomized controlled trials? (Y/N)	Does it require or recommend a specific tool, process or method for assessing risk of bias in non-randomized studies? (Y/N)	Describe any additional tools for risk of bias assessment, including the intended study design to which it should be applied (describe)	Who is responsible for performing the risk of bias assessment? (describe)	Does it describe a process for reaching consensus between assessors / resolving inter-assessor conflicts? (Y/N)
<i>Y</i>	<i>Y: "human experimental studies"</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>"Risk of bias domains used in human experimental studies that have an empirical basis, including a) sequence generation, b) allocation concealment, c) blinding, d) incomplete outcome data, and e) selective reporting. These elements have been shown in the preclinical animal literature to influence study outcomes. Our rationale was that risk of bias in a nonhuman</i>	<i>Research team</i>	<i>N</i>

experiment is comparable to risk of bias in human and preclinical animal experiments. Further, in both human and animal studies, we included a “conflict of interest” risk of bias domain.”

Overall certainty assessment

Does the framework address conduct of a certainty assessment? (Y/N)	Is a specific approach recommended or required? (describe)	What are the domains considered in this approach? (list)	How is overall certainty described (terminology)? (list categories or terms)	Does it modify or adapt a specific approach to certainty assessment? (Y/N)	How is the approach modified or adapted? (describe)	Does it provide guidance for assessing publication bias? (Y/N)	Is a specific approach recommended or required? (describe)
Y	<i>Follows GRADE, but starts at “moderate” instead of “low”</i>	<i>Risk of bias Mention GRADE but do not specify overall certainty assessment criteria</i>	<i>Known to be toxic, probably toxic, possibly toxic, not classifiable, probably not toxic</i>	Y	<i>Follows GRADE, but starts at “moderate” instead of “low”</i>	N	N/A

Reporting findings

Reporting findings			Other	Notes
Does the framework address reporting results? (Y/N)	Does it recommend or require that certain aspects of the review must be reported or presented? (Y/N) If yes, is the report published or made public?	What elements of the review must be reported? (list)	Any other framework components as described by the developer (describe)	
N	NA	NA	<i>Separation of the science from values and preferences; integration of non-human research</i>	

Additional Considerations for Framework Implementation

Disclosure of funding sources		Disclosure of author COI		Total Personnel Required	Other feasibility considerations	Notes
Does it recommend / require disclosure of any funding for the project?	How is funding disclosed?	Does it recommend / require disclosure of any individual SR team member conflicts of interest?	How are team member conflicts collected and disclosed?	What is the total # of personnel required to complete a systematic review according to the framework?	Other logistical considerations for application of the framework as described by the developer	
<i>Y: In conflict-of-interest domain</i>	NR	Y	<i>Discussed in conflict-of-interest domain</i>	<i>9 team members involved in case study</i>	<i>“Professional societies, health care organizations, and other potential guideline developers working with toxicologists can use the Navigation Guide to craft consistent and</i>	

timely recommendations to improve patient, and ultimately population, health outcomes”

Limitations & Future Research

Limitations or gaps	Description of future research priorities	Notes
Limitations or gaps in the framework as reported by developer	Description of future research priorities, next steps in framework development/testing as reported by developer	
<i>Application can be poorly executed</i>	<i>Several areas needing further development: a) rating the quality and strength of nonmammalian animal and in vitro and in silico evidence streams; b) reaching a consensus on risk of bias domains for human observational studies and nonhuman studies; c) developing well defined, measurable evidentiary bars for the factors used to downgrade the quality of environmental health evidence (i.e., indirectness, inconsistency, imprecision, and publication bias) and for upgrading human evidence (i.e., dose response, large magnitude of effect, and confounding minimizes effect); and e) exploring whether it makes a difference to the final quality rating if we assign the entire body of human observational studies a “moderate” rating and then downgrade for lesser quality study designs, or, as proposed in the NTP’s framework, we assign different types of human observational studies different ratings from the start)</i>	

NA: not applicable; NR: not reported

Supplement F. Eligible frameworks that were not sampled and rationale

Author/Year	Title	Source	Rationale
Thayer 2022	Systematic evidence map (SEM) template: Report format and methods used for the US EPA Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS) program, Provisional Peer Reviewed Toxicity Value (PPRTV) program, and other "fit for purpose" literature-based human health analyses	Database Search	Eligible but unnecessary to extract; confirmed with lead author that this publication is related to IRIS handbook, specifically the problem formulation section
Pega 2021	Systematic reviews and meta-analyses for the WHO/ILO Joint Estimates of the Work-related Burden of Disease and Injury	Hand search of references	Eligible but unnecessary to extract; based on Navigation Guide with addition of RoB-SPEO and QoE-SPEO tools
Suter 2020	Systematic review and weight of evidence are integral to ecological and human health assessments: they need an integrated framework	Database Search	Eligible but unnecessary to extract; these concepts are incorporated into IRIS
Campbell Collaboration 2021	Campbell systematic reviews: Policies and guidelines	Hand search of references	Eligible but unnecessary to extract; based on existing approaches (Cochrane) with no new information from EH
EPA 2021	Draft Systematic Review Protocol Supporting TSCA Risk Evaluations for Chemical Substances	Hand search of references	Eligible but unnecessary to extract; based on IRIS
NICE 2014	Developing NICE guidelines: the manual	Gray Literature	Eligible but unnecessary to extract; based on existing approaches (PRISMA, GRADE) with no new information from EH
WHO 2012	Handbook for Guideline Development	Hand search of references	Eligible but unnecessary to extract; based on existing approaches (GRADE) with no new information from EH